

Cinemas and Films: what can we learn from visualising historical cinema networks based on their programmes?

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This study aims to contribute to the current methodological debate on research methods using digital visualisation as its starting point while defining a specific research objective. The aim is to explore the advantages that visual network analysis can bring to the research of the history of cinema and local film circulation.

Previous research on the history of the local film culture has mostly visualised the cinema network from its geospatial perspective. The links between cinemas in geographical space as well as in a more abstract network of relationships have been analysed by many authors. Several projects within the history of cinema show the wide possibilities of visualisation that this field of research offers (Verhoeven 2016). However, these bold works are accompanied by many others, which often end up merely placing cinemas on the map. In recent years, a great emphasis has been placed on the analysis of the programming structure of cinemas. With ever-expanding databases emerging in different geographical contexts, the number of cinema historians interested in quantitative analysis and visualisation of cinema history is growing. Also, with this interest, the urge for a comparative approach towards cinema history grows (Bilteyst, Maltby, and Meers 2019; Treveri Gennari, Van de Vijver, and Ercole 2024). The structure of databases varies in each research project. However, the ground base of each such project usually consists of the list of cinemas and their programmes, that is, the films they showed and for how long. The analysis of such data primarily focuses on which films were shown in cinemas, how long they stayed on the schedule, and which ones gained significant audience response. Despite the fact that data visualization in historical research already has its tradition (Kerschbaumer et al. 2020), the research methods that take into consideration the quantitative side of cinema history are relatively scarce and unexplored in the field of cinema history. Although there have

been a number of works over the past 20 years that have attempted to quantitatively analyse as well as visualise various aspects of local cinema history, an established method for how to approach the visual analysis of historical data centred particularly on local film culture is still missing.

This paper explores the possibilities of visualizing and analysing a network of cinemas based on their relations. The analysis would not have been possible without the extensive database built as part of the transnational collaborative project, the European Cinema Audiences (ECA), which focused on researching the local history of cinemas, film culture and audiences in seven European cities in the early 1950s. We take all seven cities: Bari, Brno, Ghent, Göteborg, Leicester, Magdeburg and Rotterdam, and compare their network layouts that clearly illustrate the different conditions in which local film distribution operated and film culture existed on both sides of the Iron Wall at the beginning of the 1950s. The source database consists of almost 980,000 entries on film screenings in the seven cities in the period 1951-1953. We contrast the local film distribution and circulation operated in the Soviet bloc, where the absence of Hollywood and Western European films had an instant impact on the film culture and audiences' preferences, with that of a Western European market, where the viewers were constantly overwhelmed by the Hollywood production. These conditions led to Eastern European audiences choosing from an almost completely different range of films than Western European audiences.

The networks are not defined by the geospatial relations of the cinemas but by the relations that have emerged from their programming structures. As a starting point, we use a bipartite graph constructed from the cinemas and the films they showed. The edges are undirected and their weight is calculated as the number of screening days in a given cinema. The resulting networks give us new information about the ways in which films flow within the city and how what effect the political and social national context had on the local cases. Through the networks, we learn about the similarities between cinemas that geographically or hierarchically seem very distant, and about the new positions of cinemas within the local network that often contradict their position in the established hierarchy.

Among the main results of the proposed visual analysis is the discovery of new patterns of film circulation within the cinema network at the local level, as well as the possibility of comparing several local cases with each other. One eye-catching finding might be the absence of the comet-like tales of films attached to cinemas in Brno. In Ghent, these tails represent films that were only shown in that one cinema and then disappeared from local circulation. In Brno, such films did not exist due to state-controlled production and distribution, which resulted in a limited choice of film offerings. This also resulted in a significantly longer film trajectory compared to Ghent. The benefits that this method of network visualisation and analysis based on similarities in cinemas' programming structures entails are considered to be the most important contribution to the current debate on the methodological issues of researching and, even more importantly, comparing the histories of local film cultures. Its advantage is its applicability to cases with different

historical and political circumstances and, thus, the possibility of comparing these contexts on the basis of the networks created. Our research tests the method on cinema networks operating in the early 1950s in the free market of Western European countries, as well as on cases in Eastern Europe that were subject to state surveillance. Without condemning other types of visualization and analysis of quantitative historical data, we consider the inclusion of this method in local cinema history research to be essential for gaining a more comprehensive picture of the contemporary state of the cinema network and the processes that took place within it.

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